

IMPORTANT ADVANTAGES AND COSMETOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF SNAIL MUCIN

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Annotation: This article provides information on the important advantages of snail mutsin in cosmetology, which has its healing properties in modern medicine and folk medicine, the cosmetological function of proteins such as allantoin, collagen, elastin and hyaluronic acid in mutsin, and the classification of creams based on mutsin. data are given.

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The snail is a shell-protected gastropod that can live not only in the wild, but also at home. is a living being.

Mutsin is a family of highly glycosylated proteins that are produced by animals for adhesion, hydration, lubrication, and other functions. Animal slime can be found everywhere. But there are important advantages of the snail mucous layer. The peculiarity of snail mutsin is that it quickly affects the skin and begins to show positive results on the skin after repeated use in micro-injuries of the dermis.

Typically, snails secrete mucus in two different cases. One of these is formed during movement and is called Liposin. In the first case, the mucous membrane does not have a positive effect on the skin. The second layer of mucus is called cryptosine, which is a component of the mucous membrane that is secreted when snails are stressed or threatened, and is an important component in the production of mucus extract [1].

Mucus extract is a dry powder that is prepared on the basis of a layer of snail mucus after several stages

Snails are bred on special farms to obtain mucus extract. In the past, these creatures were subjected to unpleasant torture to obtain snail slime. Today, for this purpose, the Italian Snail Society has developed a filtration device called Muller One. To obtain snail mucus extract, the snail mucus is first separated

using a special device mentioned above. The separated mucus is filtered, cleaned and dried, then pulverized.

Due to its richness in nutrients and natural products, mucus extract is becoming important all over the world, in folk medicine and modern medicine, as well as in cosmetology. There are many cosmetic products based on snail extract for complex skin care.

The famous ancient Greek scientist and physician Hippocrates began to use mucus extract in the treatment of wounds, and it was Hippocrates who called mucus extract the extract of youth. Later, the ancient Greeks and Romans used snails for beauty treatments[2].

Cryptosine has the following functions:

- ✓ Skin protection;
- ✓ Humidifier;
- ✓ Regeneration;
- ✓ Rejuvenation;
- ✓ Bactericidal effect.

The following is information about the chemicals in cryptosine and their function.

Table 1.

s/n	Name	Function
1	Allantoin	Rich in vitamins A, C, and E, it slows down aging and deeply cleanses the skin by growing new skin cells. Prevents age-related changes.
2	Collagen	It forms the basis of the body's connective tissue, strengthens the skin and is responsible for maintaining adequate moisture retention. If collagen is reduced, the skin will suffer first, because it is the one that absorbs the most negative factors. Damaged collagen fibers cannot keep the epidermis flat and tight. The skin becomes thinner, the face sags, and wrinkles appear.
3	Elastin	Helps restore skin to its original shape when pierced or pinched or stretched. Provides firmness to epidermis
4	Hyaluronic acid	By holding water molecules and binding them to the intercellular space, it ensures the elasticity and normal functioning of tissues. Its main function is

		to maintain the water balance of all body tissues. In fact, hyaluronic acid is a gel-like substance present among our cells, one molecule of which can hold up to 500 water molecules. It is hyaluronic acid that promotes the production of collagen, which provides elasticity and softness to the skin. Hyaluronic acid is also a key ingredient in many cosmetics.
5	Copper peptides	Effectively stimulates hair growth and repairs damaged skin. Copper peptide powder is used as a cosmetic raw material
6	Chitosan	An important remedy against cardiovascular disease, injuries, infections and inflammation.
7	Mucopolysaccharides	Reduces allergic properties on the skin. Helps retain water in the skin, while maintaining proper moisture retention, along with elastin and collagen, they provide skin-appropriate firmness and elasticity.

[3,4,5].

The matrix and components of the snail's mucous membrane (collagen, elastin) are similar to human. However, the immune system is different from that of humans. The body of the snail responds to the attack of microbes not by internal inflammation, but by hydration using antimicrobial mucus, which causes systemic inflammation of the cell [6].

Aging is a cell-related process that depends on the condition of the cells, the poor condition of the cells, including improper care, chemical and artificial means, and the adverse effects of sunlight on the facial skin. many problems arise. One of the most commonly used methods to treat facial problems today is snail therapy.

In snail therapy, the snails are washed in warm water and gently applied to the face area. No need to worry during treatment. Because snails don't suck blood, they don't bite. Instead, it micro-massages and absorbs collagen into the skin. The snail produces 10 times more powerful antibiotics. As a result, the skin is cleansed, whitened, wrinkles are removed, spots, freckles, rashes, blemishes disappear, leaving the skin looking healthy. In addition to the use of snail therapy, cream products based on snail mucus and eggs have also been used as an effective remedy for many skin problems.

Figure 1. Akhatina fulika is a cream based on the appearance of albino and snail mucus and eggs.

In 1995, the first cream based on mucus worms was developed, and the Korean cosmetics company first introduced the following creams made from a mixture of snail mucus:

1. Mizon All In One Snail Repair Cream - this cream contains 92% of snail mucus and can be used at any age and on any skin type. The cream also stimulates cell division. This cream is instantly absorbed and does not cause a sticky feeling on the skin.
2. Secret Key Black Snail Original Cream - specializes in natural cosmetics and environmentally friendly ingredients, in which a special black Iberian snail is grown. prepared as a result of the addition of active additives.
3. Steblanc Black Snail Repair Cream is a high-end cream for dry and sensitive skin, containing 92% mucous worm mucus and peach extract.
4. Skin House Wrinkle Snail System Cream - the highest snail mucus, which can be used not only as a cream, but also as a massage gel and even a mask [7,8]. The cosmetological secret of the mucous membrane of the snail is that it protects the skin from ultraviolet rays and rejuvenates it with antioxidants. Increases skin elasticity and eliminates blemishes and facial wrinkles. Improves

the appearance of skin in dermatitis and rashes and removes dead skin cells. Today, snail mousse is used in the cosmetics industry in the manufacture of special moisturizing, nourishing and anti-wrinkle creams. Snail mucus does not cause allergic reactions.

In conclusion, due to the natural activity of the components, vitamins, microelements and various active compounds in the mucous membrane of the snail, its use in the treatment and prevention of many of the above cosmetological problems and many diseases possible. In addition, cosmetics imported to our country are mainly produced in foreign countries, the production of cosmetics in Uzbekistan is underdeveloped, and the bulk of some cosmetics are made by artificial and synthetic means. Our main goal is to produce cosmetic products that are effective in overcoming any cosmetological problems as a result of the action of natural active compounds in the snail mucus we are studying.

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